

THE INFLUENCE OF LANGUAGE USED ON SOCIAL MEDIA ON COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The significant development of social media has had impact on how we use the language, particularly those who actively use applications to interact with each other. This research explores how social media provides a platform for sharing ideas and experiences with vast audiences and examines the emergence of entirely new forms of language in the digital age.

INTRODUCTION

Social media's influence on our lives is undeniable in today's rapidly evolving digital world. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok have fundamentally reshaped human interaction. The way we communicate has been permanently altered. A new study, "The influence of language used in social media on communication skills" delves into the complex relationship between the digital realm and our communication practices. Social media has permeated every aspect of our daily lives. Consequently, our communication styles and the very development of language have been significantly impacted. The study investigates the intricate connection between social media and linguistic evolution. It sheds light on how online platforms have molded our communication styles and the rise of social media has revolutionized the way we interact, this has had a lasting impact not only on communication methods but also on the structure of language itself. Social media's rapid information spreading has accelerated language evolution. Character limits and instant messaging have led to the widespread adoption of abbreviations, acronyms, and emojis. This simplification streamlines online communication. The research analyzes how these linguistic changes affect how we express thoughts and feelings online. Social media connects users across geographical boundaries and language backgrounds. This has resulted in the creation of hybrid languages, combining elements of multiple tongues to form a unique digital lexicon. Our communication habits have changed due to social media's accessibility and immediacy and real-time interactions are now the norm. These are shaped by threaded discussions, multimedia content, and viral trends. These impacts span knowledge sharing, interpersonal relationships, and societal discourse. In short, the study emphasizes social media's significant role in linguistic development and communication styles. The digital age, with its capacity for linguistic innovation and democratization, has transformed language into a constantly evolving phenomenon, shaped by billions of users worldwide.

Social media fosters connection among individuals sharing common interests, beliefs, or experiences; hashtags facilitate participation in online conversations and movements, strengthening group identity and fostering a sense of belonging. Emojis transcend linguistic and cultural boundaries, conveying emotions and nuances beyond the capabilities of words, adding a personal touch and enhancing connection. Commonly used acronyms, such as LOL and BRB, have permeated everyday language, providing efficient communication and building familiarity among users. This has led to the popularization of practices such as omitting vowels ("gr8" for "great") or using symbols and numbers in place of letters ("2" for "to" or "too") (Tagliamonte, 2012).

Moreover, (Baron, 2008) states that linguistic innovation is one of the main characteristics of social media's influence on language. As a result of users on social media sites like Twitter and Instagram frequently considering their views into shorter, more succinct messages, new abbreviations, acronyms, and emoticons have been created. This highlights that nowadays the majority of youth tend to use only shortened words such as "OMG" which means "Oh my god", "BRR" be right back, or abbreviations such as:

LOL - laughing out loud	TBH - to be honest
OMG - oh my god	TTYL - talk to you later
BRB - be right back	AFAIK - as far as I know
BTW - by the way	IRL - in real life
IMO - in my opinion	DM - direct message

Abbreviations, acronyms, and shorthand expressions have become prevalent in social media discourse, allowing users to convey messages concisely (Danet & Herring, 2007). This means that the proliferation of abbreviations, acronyms, and shorthand within the dynamic ecosystem of social media discourse represents a complex interplay of linguistic pragmatics, technological constraints, and sociocultural influences. Character limits imposed by platforms like Twitter and Instagram necessitate concise expression, driving the adoption and evolution of abbreviated forms, creating a linguistic shorthand that prioritizes efficiency over orthographic completeness. This trend is further amplified by the fast-paced, asynchronous nature of online interactions, where rapid response and immediate engagement are highly valued. Consequently, established acronyms like "LOL" and "OMG," alongside emergent neologisms and context-dependent abbreviations, become integral components of online communication, fostering a sense of in-group membership and shared understanding amongst users. However, this linguistic compression carries potential drawbacks. The reliance on abbreviated forms can lead to ambiguity and misinterpretations, particularly for those unfamiliar with the evolving lexicon of social media. Moreover, the reduced grammatical complexity and formal register can potentially impact the development of more nuanced written communication skills in younger generations, raising concerns about the long-term consequences of this pervasive linguistic adaptation. Ultimately, the prevalence of abbreviated language on social media highlights the intricate relationship between language, technology, and social interaction, demanding further research into its impact on both individual communication competence and the broader evolution of language itself.

Nonetheless, if there are not any limitations this adoption of abbreviations, acronyms, and shorthand in social media communication, while enhancing speed and efficiency, harbors several significant drawbacks. The inherent brevity often sacrifices nuance and clarity, potentially leading to misinterpretations and misunderstandings, particularly in complex or sensitive conversations. This abbreviated lexicon, while fostering a sense of in-group cohesion,

simultaneously creates a barrier to entry for those unfamiliar with the constantly evolving online slang, potentially excluding less digitally fluent individuals or those from different cultural backgrounds. Furthermore, the overreliance on such concise forms can hinder the development of robust writing skills, particularly formal writing proficiency crucial for academic and professional contexts. The lack of grammatical precision and the absence of contextual cues frequently associated with more elaborate communication styles can lead to impoverished expression and a decline in the ability to articulate complex thoughts effectively. Moreover, the informal nature of this abbreviated language, while fitting within social media's often casual tone, may inappropriately bleed into formal settings, resulting in unprofessional or even offensive communication. Ultimately, while the concise nature of social media language serves a utilitarian purpose, its potential for ambiguity, exclusion, and the erosion of more sophisticated writing skills warrants critical attention and further investigation into its long-term consequences.

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